

LINGUISTIC REPRESENTATION OF VALUE ORIENTATIONS IN DIFFERENT LINGUOCULTURES

Issina Gaukhar Ilikesheva,

Doctor of Philology, Professor,

Buketov Karaganda University,

Kazakhstan, 100028, University street, 28

Zharmaganbetova Tolkyng Sagintayeva

Master student,

Buketov Karaganda University,

Kazakhstan, 100028, University street, 28

Abstract

This article is devoted to the study of verbal means of representing value orientations in different linguocultures. The work analyzes key cultural values characteristic of a particular society and expressed in language structures. The work presents examples of lexical units, proverbs, and cultural concepts that illustrate the characteristics of each of the studied cultures. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of the meanings and functions of these linguistic means, their role in maintaining cultural identity and transmitting worldview attitudes.

Keywords: value orientations, verbal means, representation, linguoculture, intercultural communication.

In modern science, the category of value orientations in various linguocultures is included in the circle of scientific interests of scientists of various fields. The relevance of this problem is explained by the intensive interaction of various cultures and languages in the conditions of the globalized world. Understanding the differences and similarities of value orientations in ethnocultural communities is important for successful intercultural communication, business, diplomacy and international relations.

Value guidelines represent social views, ideas of the collective consciousness of a particular people, passed down from generation to generation through language. Language, as the main means of communication and transmission of information, not only reflects the cultural characteristics of society, social ideals, traditions and norms of behavior, but also forms the ethnocultural consciousness of its speakers. Language performs a kind of function of integrating values.

Various cultures, in our case English-speaking, Chinese and Kazakh cultures, are vivid examples of cultural systems with different value orientations that are expressed in the linguistic picture of the world. The study of verbal means of representing values in these cultures allows not only to better understand the specifics of each language, but also to penetrate deeper into the mentality and way of life of the bearers of these cultures [1].

The culture of English-speaking countries such as the USA, Great Britain, Canada, Australia and many others has diverse and unique values that have been formed over centuries. The fundamental values that have taken root in the course of historical development in Western cultures, where special attention is paid to personal freedom and human rights, are values such as individualism, freedom, and justice.

The core value is expressed in the concepts of uniqueness and self-realization. For example, the concept of "self-made man" embodies the idea of achieving success through one's own efforts. Expressions such as "Be yourself" или "Pursuit of happiness" emphasize

the priority of personal goals. Vocabulary associated with individualism often emphasizes action and personal responsibility, demonstrating the Western understanding of freedom as a right coupled with obligations.

The concepts that characterize the social structure of life in English-speaking countries, "justice" and "fair play", represent the desire for equal opportunities for all. The expression "All men are created equal" is not just a common phrase, but a fundamental principle enshrined in culture. The emphasis on justice, respect for the rights and responsibilities of representatives of society demonstrates the importance of legal and social systems where individual rights are protected at the institutional level.

Expressions such as "Honesty is the best policy" reflect the value of transparent communication. The concept of "transparency" implies straightforwardness and honesty, which increases trust in society. Directness as a cultural norm emphasizes the importance of clear and honest dialogue in social communication. These values form the basis for a unique and dynamic culture that continues to evolve and adapt to changes in the world. English-speaking societies strive for a balance between personal freedom and collective interests, making them attractive to many people around the world.

Chinese culture, one of the oldest and richest in the world, is characterized by a system of unique values and traditions that largely determine the social order and life of the representatives of this culture. These values have been shaped by a variety of historical, philosophical and cultural factors. The key values of Chinese society are collectivism, harmony and respect for elders. These guidelines are expressed through philosophical categories and set phraseology [2].

The concepts of 和谐 (*harmony*) and 团结 (*unity*) are fundamental in the formation of social relations. Expressions like "家和万事兴" ("there is peace in the family and things are going well") emphasize the importance of agreement and harmony between people.

Harmony in Chinese culture is not only external agreement, but also internal, achieved through a balance between personal and public interests [3]. For example:

- 和气生财 – harmony brings wealth;
- 家和万事兴 – when there is peace in the family;
- 团结就是力量 – unity is strength;
- 一家人不说两家话 – members of one family

speak the same language (the importance of unity and the absence of conflicts).

The concept of 孝 (filial piety) demonstrates the nature of relationships within the family. The importance of this value is emphasized by proverbs: 百善孝为先 – *respect for elders is at the forefront of all virtues*. Respect for elders strengthens the social hierarchy and traditions of succession, ensuring the stability of society.

Concepts such as 自强不息 (*striving for the best*) emphasize the importance of continuous development, self-improvement. Hard work is interpreted as a path to achieving harmony, where personal efforts are integrated into collective success.

Key cultural concepts include such notions as 和 (*harmony*), 合作 (*cooperation*), 敬 (*respect*). One of the main categories of Chinese philosophy 道 (*Dao*) is the path that in Chinese philosophy personifies harmony with nature and society and which the surrounding world and all people should follow, the path of improvement in the implementation of a set of moral and ethical standards.

These values are the foundation of Chinese culture, ensuring its uniqueness and continuity over the millennia. Chinese society highly values harmony, order and respect, which helps it to preserve its identity and successfully adapt to modern challenges [2].

The identification of Kazakh culture is carried out in the context of its interactions with nomadic, Islamic, Russian, Central Asian and East Asian civilizations. “The mentality of the Kazakh people is a set of different features, formed at different times: patronimism and features of the Soviet mentality, and the features of paternalism as a respectful attitude to the native state, the growth of ethnic consciousness, the desire for ethnic self-identification with the people of Kazakhstan in multi-ethnic society” [4, P. 701].

The values of Kazakh culture are centered on such important concepts for society as collectivism, respect for elders, and veneration of traditions.

The concept of “*zheti ata*” (seven ancestors) symbolizes a deep connection with the family. Knowing seven generations of ancestors is a manifestation of respect for family roots. The proverb “*El birligi - el ten-digi*” (the unity of the people is the equality of the nation) emphasizes the value and importance of social unity and community support. Kazakh culture attaches great importance to social and family ties, considering them as the basis for stability. The concept of “*kona-kzhaylyk*” (hospitality) is central to Kazakh culture. The expression “*konak kelse, kut keledi*” (“luck comes with a guest”) emphasizes the sacred significance of the guest. Hospitality reflects not only a tradition, but also

a philosophy of openness and trust in interpersonal relationships. The proverb “*Ake körgen ok zhonar*” (the son does what the father did) emphasizes the transfer of experience and knowledge to the younger generation. Respect for elders helps preserve cultural heritage through generations. Kazakh proverbs emphasize the importance of social unity. For example:

- “*Tuysy berdin uysy bir*” – those who have common ancestors have one common cause;
- “*Atanyn sozi - akyldyn kozi*” – the word of the elder is the source of wisdom;
- “*Karty bar uidin kazynasy bar*” – a house with elders is a house with wealth (emphasizes the value of the experience of elders).

Kazakh society places great importance on maintaining traditions and respecting their roots, which helps preserve cultural identity and adapt to modern changes.

Thus, the study of verbal means reflecting value orientations in the English-speaking, Chinese and Kazakh linguocultures allows us to see how closely language is connected with the culture and worldview of its speakers. The culture of English-speaking countries, focusing on individualism, freedom and justice, expresses these values through concepts that emphasize the uniqueness of the individual and his or her right to self-realization. In Chinese culture, such values as collectivism, harmony and respect for elders occupy an important place, which is reflected in traditional proverbs and cultural concepts. Kazakh culture, in turn, emphasizes the continuity of generations, respect for elders and the value of hospitality, which is conveyed through the concepts of family ties and traditional relationships with society.

An analysis of verbal means of representing value orientations in various linguocultures shows that, despite the unique features and cultural characteristics of each linguacultural society, there are also universal values, such as respect for elders, the importance of family, and the importance of mutual assistance. These values, although manifested differently in each culture, emphasize the fundamental role of language in transmitting moral guidelines and maintaining cultural identity.

Understanding cultural values through language helps develop intercultural understanding and tolerance, which is especially important in today's globalized world. This kind of research helps establish a deeper cultural dialogue, allowing us to see how people of different cultures, despite their differences, strive for a harmonious and respectful society.

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